

Active HoneyFiles for Ransomware Encryption Mitigation

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Abstract—Ransomware has emerged as one of the most damaging cyber-threats, causing financial losses and data breaches across various sectors. Since detection methods are constantly improved, the ransomware itself becomes equally better in avoiding detection. This paper proposes a mitigation solution for ransomware based on HoneyFiles. The idea is that the user deploys decoy files, focusing on folders that popular ransomware is targeting. Normally, no one interacts with those files. When a process tries to open, move, delete, or rename them, the mechanism identifies the process as malicious and kills it, notifying the user accordingly. The goal is to stop the encryption functionality of ransomware. The solution was tested on Windows against 23 open-source ransomware, mitigating around 95% of them. Potentially, this approach could also protect a system against other attacks, like data breaches. Moreover, HoneyFiles are applied in the EU-funded project SecOPERA for the protection modern IoT and ICT infrastructures.

Index Terms—HoneyPots, HoneyTokens, HoneyFiles, Ransomware, Malware

I. Introduction

Cyber-security has emerged as a paramount concern in the digital age, where data is as valuable as currency and the integrity of information systems is critical for both organizations and individuals [1]. The proliferation of digital technologies has ushered in unparalleled conveniences and efficiencies, but it has also spawned sophisticated cyber-threats that evolve at a staggering pace [2], [3].

Cyber-security is vital to the financial well-being of businesses. According to a study conducted by Hiscox [4], cyber-attacks cost small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) an average of \$200,000 in 2019, and this number is steadily increasing. Implementing strong cyber-security measures helps minimize risks and enables businesses to operate securely, ensuring their continued growth. Cyber-security is also critical to protecting critical infrastructure

and public safety [5]. As previously mentioned, attacks on power grids, water treatment facilities or transportation systems can have dire consequences. By investing in strong cyber-security measures, governments and infrastructure operators can strengthen their defences against potential cyber-attacks, ensuring the stability and security of essential services. Recognizing the importance and growing threat of cyber-attacks, the cyber-security market has seen exponential growth in recent years. The global cyber-security market was valued at \$147.42 billion in 2022 and is projected to reach \$256.60 billion by 2028 [6].

Among those threats, ransomware stands out for its destructive potential and rapid growth [7]. Ransomware is a type of malicious software that encrypts a victim's files, demanding payment to restore access. Unlike other cyber-threats, which often aim to steal data or disrupt services, ransomware directly extorts victims by holding their essential data hostage. This malicious tactic has proven highly effective, with numerous high-profile attacks causing significant financial and operational damage to organizations worldwide. The impact of ransomware extends beyond financial losses, affecting healthcare services, critical infrastructure, and personal data privacy, making it a multifaceted threat to society.

Mitigation against ransomware and other cyber-threats requires a multifaceted approach, combining technology, policy, and education [8]. On the technological front, defensive measures include advanced threat detection systems, regular software updates, comprehensive backup strategies, and the implementation of security protocols, such as encryption and access control.

Among these techniques, the concept of HoneyTokens or HoneyFiles [9] has gained attention as an innovative and proactive defence mechanism. HoneyFiles are decoy files placed within a network to lure and detect unauthorized access, functioning as an early warning system against ransomware attacks. These files are designed to appear

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valuable to attackers but are monitored for any interaction, which would signal a potential breach. By deceiving attackers into revealing their presence, HoneyFiles allow organizations to respond swiftly to threats, mitigating damage and gathering intelligence on the wily methods.

This paper proposes a protection mechanisms based on Active HoneyFiles. The mechanism is continuously monitoring the interaction of processes with the deployed HoneyFiles. When an action by a non white-listing process is recorded, the mechanism intervenes and kills the malicious process. The goal is to stop the encryption functionality of ransomware and mitigate its side-effects. Therefore, an implementation of this offensive defence mechanism is presented for Windows. Open-source ransomware samples were also utilized to validate the effectiveness of the proposed solution. Moreover, this solution is developed under the EU funded project SecOPERA and is deployed in the Waste Management and Smart Watering pilot of GreenCitizens [10]. This is an SME in France with an actual system of Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructure that monitors the waste level in pipes and smart watering systems in large cities, like Paris and Marseilles. The system is operational and will be also evaluated during the Olympic Games of 2024.

The rest of the paper is organized as: Section 2 provides the background theory for ransomware and the related works for ransomware mitigation, Section 3 details the implementation of the Active HoneyFiles mechanism, Section 4 summarizes the evaluation results, Section 5 compares the proposed solution with other studies, Section 6 discusses the overall results and refers potential future work, and finally, Section 8 concludes this study.

II. Background Theory

A. The ransomware problem

Ransomware attacks now targeting organizations of all sizes, from multinationals to governments, have become numerous and making headlines [11]. A recent typical example is the attack on the Colonial Pipeline in Texas, USA [12]. The attack showed the inability of even large organizations to defend against ransomware, forcing the US President to issue an executive order to strengthen cyber-security [12]. On the other hand, the European Union through the European Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA) has repeatedly placed ransomware as one of the main threats in cyberspace [13].

Therefore, understanding the nature of ransomware and its tactics is an important primary concern in dealing with it. Addressing the threat of ransomware requires a multifaceted approach that combines preventative measures, proactive cyber-security practices, and a clear response strategy. It is essential to prioritize cyber-security awareness and training at all levels of an organization or for individual users, as one of ENISA's findings was that 84% of cyber-attacks are based on forms of social engineering [14]. Implementing strong backup systems, regularly updating

software, and using strong encryption and authentication methods are vital steps in reducing vulnerability [15]. Also, it is important to consider alternatives to paying ransom, as payment does not guarantee data recovery and fuels continued cyber criminal activity [11].

B. Related works

Through researching the relevant literature of the latest anti-ransomware tools, several solutions were identified.

1) RWGuard: RWGuard consolidates techniques proposed in earlier works into a single tool to combat ransomware [16]. To detect ransomware, RWGuard leverages individual modules to: i) check if a decoy file has been modified, ii) monitors the behaviour of certain processes, iii) detects abnormal file changes, iv) distinguishes when an encryption process is done by ransomware or by the user, and v) controls the cryptographic process by placing hooks in the Crypto-API to execute modified functions.

The RWGuard tool uses the user's original files to create HoneyTokens. The authors state that the names of the generated HoneyTokens are similar to the original user files and in such a way that the HoneyTokens stand out, without however describing the exact process. The number of decoy files is defined by the user, the list of file types is static (.txt, .doc, .pdf, .ppt, and .xls) and their contents are created by copying from the user's original files. HoneyToken file sizes are randomly selected, while the total size of decoy files is limited to 5% of normal files.

2) Rlocker: It is a software that detects the existence of ransomware on Unix operating systems. R-Locker [9] uses HoneyTokens but in a different way than usual. The recommended approach is to create a central HoneyToken in the user's Home directory, which is actually a special FIFO file, i.e. a named pipe. R-Locker then writes some bytes to this FIFO file, which will not be read until a process accesses the named pipe. Consequently, any process that tries to read the named pipe will trigger the protection mechanism and be detected. The authors suggest placing multiple symbolic links pointing to the central HoneyToken file in various system directories to reduce ransomware detection time.

Unlike other anti-ransomware systems, R-Locker interprets any read access attempt to the decoy files as ransomware activity. The false positive rate of this approach, i.e. the incidence of read access from a legitimate process, is not evaluated.

3) CryptoDrop: CryptoDrop was designed to monitor real-time changes in user data to detect ransomware attack [17]. CryptoDrop has three separate ways of identifying the ransomware attack to reduce the number of false positives, while trying to keep the number of files encrypted by the ransomware to a minimum.

File Type: Files rarely change their type or format, except when encrypted. Therefore a change in file types could be an indication that a system is under attack, although a single change in a file type is not sufficient.

So it takes quite a few changes in a short period of time to make sure there is an attack. Thus, to find the point where there are not many false positives, many tests with different ransomware are required.

Similarity hashing: Since the encrypted files are not at all similar to the original files the contents of these files can be compared with some measure of similarity. Using similarity-preserving hash functions one can see how different a file is before and after writing [18]. If the hash similarity is very disparate across many files within a certain period, there may be some ransomware activity.

Shannon Entropy: The assumed value of information in a message is called Shannon Entropy. Since encrypted data always has high entropy, this means that if many files have high Shannon entropy as a result of encryption, then this could indicate that a ransomware attack is ongoing.

These three approaches are the main methods CryptoDrop uses to detect ransomware attacks. In addition, CryptoDrop notifies if there is a lot of file deletion, as this could also indicate malicious activity. The advantage of combining these individual detection methods is that if ransomware is not detected by one, there is a chance that it will be detected by another [17].

4) Monitoring of the File System Activity with SSDT: Detecting a ransomware attack can be accomplished by monitoring system file activity [15]. The proposed method using System Service Descriptor Table (SSDT) filters input/output (I/O) requests and their attributes, such as process name, process ID, etc. So, if there are a lot of suspicious I/O requests it is very likely due to malicious processes. Finally by finding a malicious process that may be due to a ransomware, it is possible to identify the parent process of the malware and any additional process or file that the ransomware created. Then, all processes are terminated and all files are deleted.

SSDT is an "internal dispatch table" of Windows and is used to map system calls to kernel function addresses. Information returned by system calls can be read or changed by applying a technique called "hooking into the SSDT". This technique is often used by rootkits and anti-virus software. This approach claims that by applying the above technique it is very difficult not to find any suspicious activity even by future ransomware. Apart from this any attempt to stop the file tracking function is impossible as it will be able to be terminated by the system itself. So, in addition to being a fairly efficient way of detecting suspicious processes, it has such a structure that it cannot be easily bypassed by a ransomware.

III. HoneyFiles Implementation

This Section presents the proposed solution.

A. Design

In order to plan the strategy to be followed against ransomware, it is necessary to fully understand their mode of action after they manage to pass the system's

defences. Ransomware, depending on its family, targets a wide range of file types and these can be ".txt", ".doc", ".docx", ".xls", ".xlsx", ".ppt", ".pptx", ".odt", ".png", ".csv", ".sql", ".mdb", ".sln", ".php", ".asp", ".aspx", ".html", ".xml", ".psd" [19].

Files that are potential ransomware targets are either encrypted as they are detected, or their location on disk is saved to be encrypted all together at the end. Ransomware has also been observed to check for available system disks, their type (external disk, internal disk, RAM, etc.) as well as available free space. In general, they target more available internal drives and choose paths on the drive, such as C:/Users/ and subfolders [19], while avoiding directories, such as Windows, Program Files, and \$Recycle.bin [20]. The order in which files are encrypted and the disk paths are traversed is in Windows-1252 or vice versa, sometimes based on size or randomly [19]. Finally, there are three ways for file encryption [21]:

- Write-in-place: creates a temporary file and encrypts the target folder, writes the encrypted data of the target folder to the new folder, and rewrites the contents of the new folder to the targeted one and deletes it.
- Rename-and-encrypt: renames the target folder, encrypts the data as in the previous case, and renames the target to its original name.
- Create-encrypt-and-delete: creates a file, encrypts the target folder's data in it, and deletes the target.

Taking all these into account, to get the best possible and fastest results our HoneyFiles should: i) consist of files that will be placed mainly in the C:/Users/ path of the disk, ii) consist of various types of files, (".doc", ".xls", etc.), iii) be named so if encryption order followed is in Windows-1252, be encrypted first or vice versa, and iv) have a size corresponding to the encryption order (e.g., in ascending order, the file size should be small).

Finally, the defensive mechanism should emphasize the opening of the files as all three encryption methods require access to its contents. At the same time, attention should be paid to renaming, creating, and deleting files.

B. Restart Manager

At first, a mechanism will have to be found which will be able to track the changes made to the HoneyFiles placed on the disk. For Windows Operating System (OS), the use of the Restart Manager API was chosen. Restart Manager is a library designed to reduce required OS restarts during software updates. Files that may be modified during an update may have been "locked" by applications, preventing the update process. This can lead to a system reboot forcing applications to release the files they have locked. In contrast, the Restart Manager allows processes to release files by terminating the processes using them, if the required conditions are met [22].

1) Source process: Each OS has a unique way of handling concurrent file access. In the case of Windows, depending on how a file is opened, a process may have exclusive access to the file, such as in the case of file mapping or files opened without the `FILE_SHARE_READ` — `FILE_SHARE_WRITE`. In such cases, the file may be "locked" by the process, causing other processes requesting read or write access to that file to be denied. If other processes need access to a "locked file", they can request a reboot of the entire system to free the file causing user operations to be interrupted. To solve this problem, starting with Windows Vista, Microsoft introduced Restart Manager, allowing applications to terminate resource-locking processes without requiring a restart.

2) Utilizing the Restart Manager: Restart Manager is implemented on Windows through the "Rstrtmgr.dll" library, located in `C:\Windows\System32\`. Processes interact with the Restart Manager through "sessions". In each session, a set of resources (files, processes, services) is registered and information related to them is obtained. The above resources represent targets that must be accessed by a process. The Restart Manager's role is to determine which processes are currently blocking a particular resource, referred to as an affected application, and store the information about the applications in a list. In this way, it is possible to design a program where, through a Restart Manager session, a set of files, processes or services that must be used can be registered, to determine which processes block their access. If there are, Restart Manager will provide the list of affected applications and the program may request that these applications be shut down. An extension of this program is to monitor resources that will act as HoneyFiles and when any activity (e.g., opening and encryption) is observed in them to terminate each process.

3) HoneyFile mechanism implementation: The first step in implementing the application is to call the `RmStartSession` function to create the Restart Manager session. The function returns a session handle and a session key which are necessary in the next steps. After the session has been created, the system resources to be monitored can be registered by calling the `RmRegisterResources` function. A resource can be a file, a process or a service. In this case, we will use files as these are what most ransomware targets, although some ransomware have been observed to specifically terminate Windows Services before encryption [23]. Then, after the resources to be monitored have been successfully registered, using the `RmGetList` function returns a list of `RM_PROCESS_INFO` structures as well as the number of processes used by HoneyFiles. As long as the number is zero, this means that there is no access. But if it changes, then there may be a breach of the system. Thus, by traversing the elements of the list returned by the `RmGetList` function, the ID of its respective process can be found. The ID is information found in the `RM_PROCESS_INFO` structure. By accessing a

process object, it is possible to find the location of the path inside the disk where the application that uses our resource is located, i.e., the location on the disk where the ransomware is located, and terminate it. Here, it should be noted that there are 7 `RM_APP_TYPE` types, one of which is critical and can only be terminated by shutting down the system. This is shown in Figure 1, where we see that the application type is 1000, therefore critical, and it is an openssl encryption command executed in an Ubuntu terminal environment using the Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL).


```
C:\Users\PC\Desktop\ConsoleApplication1\64\Debug\ConsoleApplication.exe
0. Application Type = 1000
0. App Name = System
0. Process Id = 4
```

Fig. 1. RM APP TYPE 1000 – OpenSSL encryption process.

Thus, whenever a change occurs in HoneyFiles, the legal user of the system is informed via email. This is done by leveraging the Canarytoken service [24]. The Canarytoken enables the implementation of different kinds of tokens, such as Microsoft Word Document, PDF, QRCode, SQL SERVER, and DNS Token [24].

However, after conducting experiments consisting of scripts simulating a typical ransomware operation, two weaknesses were observed. The first and most important can be perceived both experimentally and logically. It has to do with the way ransomware encrypts data. If the ransomware follows the Rename-and-encrypt process, i.e., rename the HoneyFile before encryption, because the HoneyFile is listed in the monitored resources list with a different name and path, it is not possible to detect the malicious process in a resource that does not exist. The second weakness has to do with the size of the HoneyFile. If the size of the HoneyFile is too small (<10MB) the opening and encryption are done very quickly and the program cannot detect the process. This changes from computer to computer as it depends on its performance.

4) Dealing with constraints: To deal with the inability to detect the ransomware when the name of HoneyFile has been changed, the solution was given by using the `System.IO.FileSystemWatcher` class [25]. This class claims to enable tracking changes, such as open/delete/rename, to a disk path. An additional feature of the class is that it can set filters on the monitored files. Such filters can be file names and file types. Utilizing and evaluating the class, it was noticed that it is not possible to define an entire disk as a path, but a part of it. This is not much of a limitation as as mentioned earlier most ransomware targets the path `C:/Users/...`, which can be monitored. Another limitation that must be addressed is how the monitoring system will distinguish HoneyFiles from files used by the user or non-malicious system applications. This is to avoid as many false positive violations as possible. The solution

given is that the tracked files should contain a common string in their name but such that the ransomware will not realize that the files are HoneyFiles (e.g., Honeybait.odt, ransomwarebait.txt). For the performed tests, the name "test*" was used to solve the problem and to prove that the designed solution is possible. Thus, every test whose name will contain the word/string test will be tracked. The HoneyFile's performance was confirmed by running scripts that simulate the three file encryption cases.

However, the design of anti-ransomware applications must also anticipate the possible ways in which detection mechanisms can be circumvented. In this case, since HoneyFiles are used, it should be considered how a ransomware can understand if a file is a HoneyFile. So for HoneyFiles to be more efficient:

- 1) Their size should not be too big or too small. Such behaviour has been observed in an Android ransomware, SLocker, where files smaller than 150KB and larger than 50MB were not encrypted.
- 2) HoneyFiles regardless of their size should not be filled with zeros as it is easy for ransomware to detect.
- 3) Ransomware can lie dormant before it begins to encrypt a target system's files. During this time they can observe which files the user is using and which are not. This can lead a ransomware to suspect that the latter are HoneyFiles. If a ransomware exploits a mechanism similar to FileSystemWatcher or exploiting the Master File Table (MTF), which contains file information such as date created, last access, attributes, it can see which files are not in use and avoid encrypting them by making them HoneyFiles useless. This can be circumvented by creating a mechanism that will periodically and randomly change some elements such as last access or simulate their use by the user. The effectiveness of this mechanism may be a subject for further study.

IV. Evaluation

In this Section there is an in-depth analysis of how the tests were carried out to evaluate the designed tool.

A. Test environment

First, a test environment capable of testing the designed ransomware detection and countermeasures had to be selected. In addition, it should provide the corresponding protection of the physical computer and also be able to be configured in a short time to test different ransomware. For this reason Windows Sandbox was chosen. Windows Sandbox provides a lightweight environment for securely running applications for Pro, Enterprise, and Education Windows users. At the same time it maintains access to the Internet which is important as it allows active ransomware to communicate with their servers allowing their full cycle of operation.

The advantage of the test environment was that it can ensure that ransomware does not spread unchecked either to the physical machine or to the rest of the network. Furthermore, since the ransomware binaries are stripped of their extensions, and downloaded directly into the Sandbox, it is not possible to accidentally run the ransomware on the physical machine. A typical procedure for running a test is: i) start Windows Sandbox, ii) download all the necessary files, iii) execution of the central Script, and iv) wait 20 minutes to run the file check Script to record the encrypted files and check the reaction of the tool.

The process is quite automated as apart from downloading and installing the required files, the rest of the process was controlled by a central Script as previously described. It should be noted that although the final tool allows each user to enter their own parameters (e.g., CanaryToken, creation and removal of HoneyToken) in the experimental process these were done automatically by the tool to speed up the whole process. However, even though the test conditions were the same, sometimes the Scripts needed tweaking to achieve the desired result, while other times some ransomware samples caused problems with memory and connecting to the Sandbox and the test was repeated.

B. Ransomware samples

After successfully dealing with Scripts simulating a ransomware it was decided to test the effectiveness of the designed tool on real ransomware. There are many online repositories where a researcher can gain special access, such as virusshare or hybrid-analysis. However, due to the special access required, other open sources with executable ransomware binaries from GitHub were selected, such as theZoo [26], malware-samples [27], malware-samplelibrary [28], and ransomware-Samples [29]. This made it possible to obtain a wide range of ransomware, from the beginning until 2023. These include ransomware families, like WannaCry, TeslaCrypt, Locky, CryptoLocker, and Petya. To avoid wasting resources and time in testing inactive ransomware, and ransomware that did not work, a preliminary analysis was performed on the ransomware before the actual testing with the detection method. At this stage, using a central control Script corresponding to a real test, the following procedure was followed:

- 1) Start Windows Sandbox.
- 2) Downloading all necessary files including the ransomware, Scripts that create random files in certain folders, checking for their existence after the ransomware is executed, and the central control Script.
- 3) Execution of the central Script which implements in the following order: i) the Script that creates random files (name, type, size) at specific folders, ii) the execution of the ransomware, and iii) the execution of the Script control of the files that were created.

- 4) Wait 5 minutes to run the File Check Script created to record the encrypted files and check if the ransomware is working.

The wait was chosen to be 5 minutes as a ransomware immediately starts its destructive action. Therefore, if no changes are observed during this time, it may be because the ransomware either has a dormant period, is unable to run which may be the result of a corrupted executable file, or is generally an inactive ransomware. In either case, it would not be suitable for further testing and was marked as inactive. The number of active ransomware reached 23.

C. Test computer

The test environment responsible for testing the ransomware consists of a physical computer and a virtual one. The characteristics of the physical computer are: CPU: AMD Ryzen 5 2600; RAM: 16GB 2600Hz CL 16-18-18; Storage: SSD Read Speed 560 MB/s Write Speed 510 MB/s Maximum 4KB Random Write 90000 IOPS; and OS: Windows 10 Education. The physical Windows 10 Education PC was fully updated and sleep mode was disabled to ensure that the test environment would not close during the test. The physical computer has two functions. The first is to run the virtual machines and second is to provide all the necessary files mentioned earlier. The features of the virtual computer were limited to: RAM: 4GB; Storage: 50GB; and Data: 1 shared folder with the necessary files from the physical computer. To make the virtual test system look like a real system, a set of programs that are often featured on a Windows PC were installed, like: Google Chrome, Sublime, Spotify, VLC media player, Winrar, and Java. When the above programs were installed, the test system was ready.

D. HoneyFile evaluation

Initially, the idea was to create random files (name, type, size) in all subfolders of the virtual machine. However, this idea did not proceed for two reasons: the complexity of such an approach and the overlooking of a feature that should have HoneyFiles and consequently also regular files, i.e., not to consist of files that will be filled with zeros. For this, it was chosen to use normal files of the most common types of documents, word, pdf, images, etc., where the size starts from a few kilobytes and reaches several megabytes. These were then placed in the Windows user's Desktop, Documents, Downloads, and Videos subfolders, folders that as previously mentioned are a common target of ransomware. The number of files placed in each folder is 100. The HoneyFiles were created in exactly the same way and placed in the same subfolders. The number of HoneyFiles in each subfolder is 10. Obviously, with the use of HoneyFiles, the higher the number, the more likely it is to detect the ransomware and the faster the results. Generally, HoneyFiles cannot be large as they take up disk space, especially in our case where they must be larger than 15MB. The names in the HoneyFiles were given so

that they are distributed throughout the English alphabet, so regardless of the order of encryption, there is a chance that they will be encrypted first.

E. HoneyFile application

The designed tool is controlled by a Command Line Interface where the user can enter his own parameters. The user in order to be notified via the CanaryToken service must create their own DNS CanaryToken and pass it as a parameter. If he does not enter it, the tool continues to work normally, however the user will not receive a notification in his email. Figure 2 shows the function "1 - Enter DNS CanaryToken" where the CanaryToken is entered. Then the user can create the HoneyFile files. It has two options, either to create in a system folder a group of 8 predefined files or to create them one by one giving their location on the disk followed by their name. The functions "2 - Create Default HoneyTokens", "3 - Create HoneyToken by path" described are shown in Figure 2. In both cases the user is asked to specify the size of the files to be created. At this point the user can activate the tool to start the ransomware detection process. Once the detection process has started it can be terminated at any time by pressing "Enter". Finally, the user can see all the Honeytoken files in the system with the option "5 - Print list of HoneyTokens" but also delete any of them you wish, option "4 - Remove HoneyToken.". Figure 2 shows a successful detection of the WannaCry ransomware.

At this point, it should be mentioned that of the 23 active ransomware collected, 19 were detected in time so that the ransomware did not cause much damage, 3 were detected at an advanced stage having encrypted up to 27% of the total files, and 1 was detected after the completion of its action cycle.

V. Comparison

In this Section, the approaches of the four papers mentioned in Section 2 and our HoneyFiles are reviewed. The comparison is based on the following 5 key categories.

Methodology: Each method describes its approach to ransomware detection. This can include false targets, process monitoring, file type checks, etc.

Ransomware Families Tested: Lists the specific ransomware families used for testing. This is important to understand the scope of the results.

Detection Accuracy: Percentage of ransomware samples correctly detected by the method. This gives an idea of the effectiveness of the method in detecting malware.

False Positives: The percentage of detections that presented false alarms, i.e., cases where the method detected something as malicious but actually was not.

Limitations and Future Improvements: Here the problems and possibilities for improvement of the method are described. This may include improving accuracy, reducing false positives, or addressing further limitations.

TABLE I
Qualitative comparison of ransomware mitigation mechanisms

Mechanism	Approach	Ransomware families tested	Accuracy	False positives	Limitations and Future improvements
RWGuard	Fake targets, process monitoring, user encryption learning	14 ransomware families (Wannacry, Cerber, CryptoLocker, etc.)	It is not explicitly stated but describes that it has zero false positives	False positives are 0.1%, with a minimal additional performance cost of 1.9%.	Improved time delay and custom encryption handling
RLocker	HoneyFiles on Linux OS	2 ransomware samples and proof of concept tools	100% as all samples were detected	False positives occur which can be limited with blacklists	Improved false positives and applicability on Windows and Android
CryptDrop	File type checking, similarity hashing, Shannon entropy	492 ransomware samples from 14 different families	100% detection 0.2% file loss	Inability to check for false positives	Optimization of false positives and way of monitoring
MFSA	Suggest SSDT monitoring for suspicious I/O requests	1.389 ransomware samples from 15 different families	–	–	–
HoneyFiles (this study)	HoneyFiles on Windows OS	23 samples from 8 families	95% valid detection	No mechanism to measure false positives	More efficient monitoring, list of non-malicious processes

Fig. 2. Deployment of HoneyTokens & Detection of WannaCry.

Table I summarizes the comparative results. This qualitative analysis provides an overview of the different approaches to ransomware detection presented in the selected papers. Understanding the strengths, weaknesses, and details of each method is essential to guide future research and create more reliable and adaptive ransomware

detection systems.

VI. Discussion and Future Work

With this work, an attempt was made to highlight the ever-increasing risk of cyber-attacks, as well as the need to deal with them, focusing on ransomware. This effort led to the implementation of a solution which will not only be able to detect the existence of ransomware, but will also give the possibility to identify the process responsible for the encryption and consequently the ransomware itself and its location on the disk.

The RM API and FSW class can work cooperatively monitoring shared HoneyFiles offering maximum coverage but also autonomously. Finally, in an effort to optimize HoneyFiles so that they cannot be detected by ransomware, we set some general rules which are: i) consist of files of different sizes and have a HoneyFile with the largest and smallest size in a folder, ii) consist of files of different types, iii) the name should not betray their status and there should be HoneyFiles where their name will start with the first and last character in Windows-1252 series, iv) they must not be dummy files containing zeros or their content is encrypted, and v) there must be a mechanism that will simulate their periodic use.

Furthermore, the Active HoneyFile solution could be utilized against other cyber-threats as well. In data breaches, an attacker would transfer high-volumes of data out of the legitimate system. This would include read, move, or copy operations on those files. Therefore, when the malicious processes would try to steal a HoneyFile, the protection mechanism would terminate the wily actions and alarm the user. Moreover, in the case where somehow the attacker had successfully extracted a HoneyFile, the fact that in the suggested implementation the HoneyFiles are also Canarytokens, means that the user would be at least notified when the attacker would try to open it.

VII. Conclusions

This work presented a defensive mechanism to detect a running ransomware and mitigate its side-effects by blocking its encryption process. The solution is based on Active HoneyFiles, which are decoy files deployed by the legitimate user throughout the file-system. A mechanism observes the processes that try to interact with these files, and if the processes are not white-listed, it terminates them. Therefore, when a ransomware starts encrypting files, the mechanism will identify the interaction when a HoneyFile is about to be encrypted, killing the encryption process automatically. The damage is stopped at this point and the user is notified to take further actions (i.e., perform an anti-virus scan to delete other counterparts of the malware). The Active Files are implemented for the Windows OS. A testbed was created where open-source versions of ransomware were tested. Out of the 23 ransomware samples that were evaluated (e.g., WannaCry, Petya, and CryptoLocker), the proposed solution managed to successfully mitigate 22 of them. The Active HoneyFiles were implemented under the EU funded project SecOPERA and are deployed on an actual IoT infrastructure of the waste management and smart watering pilot. The pilot takes place in several cities of France and the solution will be active during the Olympic Games of 2024. Moreover, apart from ransomware, this mechanism could potentially counter other cyber-threats as well, such as data breaches (i.e., detect and terminate a process, when it tries to read or copy a HoneyFile).

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References

- [1] A. Hussain, et al., "A Review on Cybersecurity: Challenges & Emerging Threats". 3rd International Conference on Networking, Information Systems & Security (NISS), ACM, article 28, 2020, pp. 1-7.
- [2] G. Assenza, et al., "Cyber threats for operational technologies". International Journal of System of Systems Engineering, Inderscience, vol. 10, 2020, pp. 128-142.
- [3] Z. A. E. Houda, "Cyber Threat Actors Review: Examining the Tactics and Motivations of Adversaries in the Cyber Landscape". Cyber Security for Next-Generation Computing Technologies, Taylor & Francis, 1st edition. 2024
- [4] Hiscox Cyber Readiness Report 2019. 2019. url: <https://www.hiscox.com/documents/2019-Hiscox-Cyber-Readiness-Report.pdf>.
- [5] U. P. D. Ani, H. He, and A. Tiwari, "Review of cybersecurity issues in industrial critical infrastructure: manufacturing in perspective". Journal of Cyber Security Technology, Taylor & Francis, vol. 1, issue 1, 2017, pp. 32-74.
- [6] Statista: Cybersecurity - Worldwide. url: <https://www.statista.com/outlook/tmo/cybersecurity/worldwide#revenue>.
- [7] S. Razaula, et al., "The Age of Ransomware: A Survey on the Evolution, Taxonomy, and Research Directions". IEEE Access, IEEE, vol. 11, 2023, pp. 40698-40723.

- [8] M. Cen, et al., "Ransomware early detection: A survey". Computer Networks, Elsevier, vol. 239, article 110138, 2024, pp. 1-20.
- [9] J.A. Gómez-Hernández, L. Álvarez-González, and P. García-Teodoro. "R-Locker: Thwarting ransomware action through a honeyfile-based approach". In: Computers And Security, Elsevier, vol. 73, 2018, pp. 389-398.
- [10] Secure OPEN source softwarE and hardwaRe Adaptable framework (SecOPERA), EU funded project, GA-101070599, 2023-2025. url: <https://secopera.eu/pilot-2/>.
- [11] ENISA Threat Landscape 2022. url: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-threat-landscape-2022>.
- [12] Colonial Pipeline hack explained: Everything you need to know. url: <https://www.techtarget.com/whatis/feature/Colonial-Pipeline-hack-explained-Everything-you-need-to-know>.
- [13] ENISA Threat Landscape 2021. url: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-threat-landscape-2021>.
- [14] ENISA Threat Landscape 2020 - Main Incidents. url: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/enisa-threat-landscape-2020-main-incidents>.
- [15] A. Kharraz, et al. "Cutting the Gordian Knot: A Look Under the Hood of Ransomware Attacks". Detection of Intrusions and Malware, and Vulnerability Assessment, Ed. by M. Almgren, V. Gulisano, and F. Maggi, Springer, 2015, pp. 3-24.
- [16] S. Mehnaz, A. Mudgerikar, and E. Bertino. "RWGuard: A Real-Time Detection System Against Cryptographic Ransomware". Research in Attacks, Intrusions, and Defenses (RAID), Springer, 2018, pp. 114-136.
- [17] N. Scaife et al. "CryptoLock (and Drop It): Stopping Ransomware Attacks on User Data". 36th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS), IEEE, 2016, pp. 303-312.
- [18] J. Kornblum. "Identifying almost identical files using context triggered piecewise hashing". Digital Investigation, Elsevier, vol. 3, 2006, pp. 91-97.
- [19] J. Lee, J. Lee, and J. Hong. "How to Make Efficient Decoy Files for Ransomware Detection?" International Conference on Research in Adaptive and Convergent Systems (RACS), ACM, 2017, pp. 208-212.
- [20] Y. Lemmou, J.-L. Lanet, and E. M. Souidi. "A behavioural in-depth analysis of ransomware infection". IET Information Security, IET, vol. 15, issue 1, 2021, pp. 38-58.
- [21] A Different View: Understand and Prevent Encrypting Ransomware. 2015. url: <https://www.paloaltonetworks.com/blog/2015/01/different-view-understand-prevent-encrypting-ransomware/>.
- [22] About Restart Manager. url: <https://learn.microsoft.com/enus/windows/win32/rstmgr/about-restart-manager>.
- [23] Deception Engineering: exploring the use of Windows Service Canaries against ransomware. 2021. url: <https://research.nccgroup.com/2021/03/04/deception-engineering-exploring-the-use-of-%20windows-service-canaries-against-ransomware/>.
- [24] Canarytokens Guide. url: <https://docs.canarytokens.org/guide/>.
- [25] FileSystemWatcher Class. url: <https://learn.microsoft.com/enus/dotnet/api/system.io.filesystemwatcher?view=net-7.0>.
- [26] Mori.RT Labs, 'theZoo - A Live Malware Repository', 2014-2024. url: <https://github.com/ytisf/theZoo>.
- [27] InQuest, 'malware-samples', 2018-2024. url: <https://github.com/InQuest/malware-samples>.
- [28] Mustafa Kaan Demirhan, 'malware-sample-library', 2019-2024. url: <https://github.com/mstfknn/malware-sample-library>.
- [29] Mohsen KHashei, 'Ransomware-Samples', 2021-2024. url: <https://github.com/kh4sh3i/Ransomware-Samples>